

Research

Aging and Elderly Care Services in Developing Nations; Descriptive Analysis of Services Offered in China and Pakistan

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Abstract: *Aging is a global issue which has impact over the world population. Aging is on rise in Pakistan as well since early 1990s due to the onslaught of demographic transition in the country. This situation has posed many problems not only for the senior citizens, but their relatives and families as well due to the varying socio-economic environment. Pakistan, a country in South Asia and in neighborhood of China, is the fifth most populous country in the world with an estimated population over 220 million people. Traditionally, senior citizens tend to live with their children as youngsters were socially responsible for the upkeep of the elders but shifts in age demographics, family structures and migration patterns may see the aged population being left behind. Modernization and urbanization have had a major impact on the life of elders in Pakistan and it's not always a positive effect. Senior citizens demand and desire time with their children and grandchildren. The issues faced by elders in Pakistan is highly correlated with modernization and change in the socio-economic factors. In a poorly developed country like Pakistan, this responsibility has to be shouldered by the state due to changing cultural conditions and the deteriorating grip of religion. This facts and data used in this paper is based on the research results of previous research papers which are mentioned and cited in this paper. This research paper describes aging and elderly care in Pakistan in comparison with China along with the lessons that can be learnt from China as it is an aging society and the way China has developed long term care policy and services for its senior citizens. This paper concludes that the prospects of elderly care services in Pakistan depends on the commitment and ability of the government in meeting the challenges of insufficient funds for social services, inadequate and low-quality provision, and the lack of seriousness in making and implementing social policy for the betterment of senior citizens.*

Keywords: *Aging, elderly care, senior citizens, social services, modernization, socio-economic problems*

Introduction

Aging is not only problematic itself but also have severe socio-economic repercussions for the societies across the globe. Sociologists have described four reasons that why aging is disastrous for people as well as for the society. Firstly, it pulls out people from active employment; secondly, it devitalizes the human body, thirdly it takes away nearly all of physical pleasures from people, and fourthly it is takes us closer to death. However, two more reasons, economic insecurity and loneliness, can be included in this list. Normally, economic, social, physiological and emotional difficulties are associated with old age.

Aging is usually defined in terms of four important aspects; i-e, chronological age, physiological, psychological and social. Chronological age is defined as the time spent since the birth of a person measured in years and it is the utmost common factor of age and aging (Birren and Schroots, 1995). Physiological age comprises of the study of changes in various physiological systems and how these changes affect the physical, psychological, and social functioning of elder people. Psychological age describes the individual's ability to get familiarize with and able to alter acquainted and unacquainted situations. These circumstances may include an individual's physical and intellectual aptitudes as well as person's dynamic ability and behavior. Lastly, social age defines the role of an individual in a given social arrangement where age-based consigned roles stipulate an individual's privileges and responsibilities as well as person's ability to relate to and connect with other people. It also interprets how elders are required to perform in a society (Birren: 1969).

Pakistan's society has always been considered for great ethics, esteem and respect for human life. When someone reaches an old age, he or she has been regarded as a symbol of respect, astuteness, and virtue. The main reason for this attitude is credited to the strong bonds existing through the joint family system fostered by religious Islamic values that glorifying the status of the senior citizens of the society. Pakistan's constitution also asserts the promotion of the social and economic well-being of its people as a principal and precious objective that makes it the most significant obligation on the state to provide the basic needs of life for citizens who are perpetually or provisionally unable to earn their living on account of oldness, frailty, illness or unemployment (Saba, 2004).

The impact of socio-economic pressures and urbanization has changed lifestyles all across the globe. Pakistan has also been affected by this globally changing trend especially for the household unit. More people are trying to have small and independent family units. In many cases, people have reorganized family structures as the joint family system is becoming unpopular and is causing social disturbance among youngsters. Today, employment anxieties, transfers and posting, and relocation have contributed to this change in family structure ideology. Moreover, in present socio-economic conditions in developing countries like Pakistan, many people find that family support is diminishing which affects the elderly care as government welfare systems are almost non-existent (Khalid Salahuddin, 2006).

According to United Nation Population Fund report of 2012, the second decade of the century (2011-2020) shall witness about one billion people over the age of 60 years. According to the UN estimates, the population of senior citizens (aged 60+) will grow to 1.2 billion by the year 2025. By 2050, the planet will have 2.5 billion senior citizens and almost two third of these elderly people will be living in developing countries. In countries like Japan and China, very old (aged 80+) people have become the fastest growing population and these statistics can't be ignored (UNPF Report, 2012).

This worldwide rise in the elderly population has also made an impact on Pakistan. Despite the political and economic instabilities, life expectancy in Pakistan has been successfully improved which is evident by the growth of the elder population. In 1998, the World Health Organization (WHO) report estimated that approximately 6% of the Pakistani population was over than 60 years of age which might get doubled by 2025. Almost three decades ago, on average people last 50 years which by the end of current decade will rise up closer to 72 years (Goodkind, 2015).

Being fifth most populous country of the world, Pakistan plays a pivotal role in the world. Its population is approximately over 220 million people according to the 2017 census, trailing just behind Indonesia and slightly ahead of Brazil. Between 1950 and 2011, Pakistan's urban population expanded over seven-folds, while the total population increased by over four-folds. In the past, the country's population had a relatively high growth rate of 2.4% that has now been changed by moderate birth rates between 1998 and 2017 (World Population Prospects: The 2017 Revision, 2017). According to a UN report published in 1996, Pakistan will become the fourth most populous country of the world by the year 2050.

Pakistan as a developing country is passing through many challenges, among them, the process of a demographic transition is the most thriving one. The major concern is the ratio of aged people with respect to the total population which is rising day by day. According to 1998 Census report, in Pakistan the population of over-60 years increased to 7.34 million (GoP, 1999). This indicated three times increase in the aged population over 3.5 decades. It was further reported that by the year 2030, it would be increased to 23.76 million. This shows the increment in the share of the elderly in total population 9.3 percent by the year 2030. According to OECD/World Bank, from 1990 to 2008, the population of Pakistan increased by 23 million, with a 54% growth in population compared to India and Bangladesh, which are 34% and 38%, respectively (IEA, 2010).

Global Perspective of Senior Citizens

The United Nations Population Division and United Nations Population Funds has released several updated reports based on the world population. These reports highlight the impact of an increasing population of people aged 65 and older. In July 2005, the world had 6.5 billion inhabitants, 380 million more than in 2000 with a gain of 76 million annually. Despite the declining fertility levels projected over 2005–2050, the world population is expected to reach 9.1 and will still be adding 34 million people annually by this mid-century. Today, 95% of all population growth is absorbed by the developing world and just 5% by the developed countries. By 2050, the population of more developed countries as a whole would be declining slowly by about one million people each year and that of the developing world would be increasing by 35 million annually, 22 million of whom would be living in the least developed countries. The elderly population in developed countries has already surpassed the number of children (aged below 15). By 2050, there will be two senior citizens per child. In the developing countries, the proportion of the population aged 60 or over is estimated to rise from 8% in 2005 to about 20% by the year 2050 (Zlotnik, 2005).

The developing countries, mainly those profoundly indebted, have plunged into great problems as a result of the global economic recession and the process of globalization. The withdrawal of subsidies on essential commodities and continuing denial of market access to exports have had a negative impact on the overall economic and social conditions in developing countries. The vulnerable groups, especially the senior citizens, had been mostly affected. Thus, most of the countries have not attained the targets/commitments made under the International Plan of Action for aged population adopted in 1982 in Vienna” (Salahuddin & Jalbani, 2006).

This clearly indicates the gap in achieving the desired level of progress for the elder population. This is the opportune time that developing and developed nations should realize their role in looking after the best interests of senior citizens. On the basis of key lessons that have drawn from a post First World Assembly era, the challenges ahead in the new millennium should be met with improved foresight and commitment. Our prime consideration should be to advocate for the well-being of the elderly population by promoting dignity, equality, non-discrimination, free society, better healthcare, and above all by breaking the vicious circle of poverty (Ahsan, 2002).

It is clear that for the benefit and help of senior citizens and local people, many societies fund different community activities and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), as well as other efforts. This implies that social funds are seen as complementary factors and part of broader social policies, rather than the entirety of social policies. It suggests more than a marginal role, but one whereby the emphasis of some of the social funds is that of distributing grants to projects and services of community organizations and NGOs in a smaller scale. When social funds are in a complementary role, this increases the possibilities to envisage innovative mechanisms for the financing social funds.

In China, for example, The National Social Security Fund in China is a government-run investment fund established primarily to provide a reserve of funds for China's social security system which is managed by the National Council for Social Security Fund. Social services in China are mainly decentralized. Local governments, especially from the more developed provinces, are responsible for financing, designing and delivering mandatory social services, social assistance, education and community services. The Chinese Central Government formulates and issues policy directives, standards and regulations to encourage local governments to share good practices. However, in some cases local governments are short of budget and are unable to meet the policy standards formulated by the central government, which results in the development of uneven, inadequate social services across cities, towns and villages (Mountfield & Wong, 2005).

Senior Citizens in China

China has emerged as an economic and political superpower. It is the second largest economy in the world, yet its per capita GDP is only that of a medium-income state. Despite these impressive achievements, social development is still considered to be uneven and to lag behind economic development. Higher risk of income loss or shock due to social dislocation, insecure employment,

and inadequate social protection are the major challenges faced by the Chinese people (Leung & Wong, 2012).

One of the major socioeconomic challenges for China is the fast aging of its population. China is now called an aging society yet it is still considered as a medium-income society. According to the 2010 census, China has 1.41 billion people. The number of those aged over 60 has reached 180 million, accounting for 13% of the population overall (Leung & Wong, 2012). Coupled with the market-driven reform of social services and rapid erosion of family support, the provision of affordable and accessible long-term care (LTC) services to older people has already become an urgent issue to be tackled by the government (Leung & Wong, 2012).

The key features of China's aging population are its large size; the rapidity of the overall aging process; and the significant regional, gender, and rural-urban differences (Information Office, State Council, 2006). Since the urbanization rate continues to speed up from 50% in 2010 to estimated 70% by 2050, rural-urban migration, particularly among young people, will increase the old age dependency ratio in rural areas still further. By 2050, this may have exceeded 60%, compared with 30% in urban areas (Leung & Wong, 2012).

Family support for older people is a historical and appreciated Chinese tradition. The Chinese constitution, Criminal Law, Marriage Law, as well as the Law on the Protection of the Rights and Interests of Older People, all recommend that society and family have a responsibility to take care of their elders. These laws strive to realize the ideals of providing support, medical care, entertainment, education, and opportunities for achievement to older people (Leung & Wong, 2012). However, recently there has been sharp decline in the trend of elders living with children due to massive urbanization and people interested in small size families due to expensive cost of living. As a result of this trend, larger numbers of older people find themselves living alone, and with family support eroding, more and more elders have to face the risk of being poor and socially excluded.

In terms of health care, the modernized health care insurance program has lesser coverage and is further dependent on fee payments. Even though health services remain largely publicly provided, they are increasingly privately financed (Leung & Wong, 2012). With the phenomenal increases in medical fees, even people with health insurance may find the charges for care unaffordable. Overall, the modernized health care system is marked by high inequality and inadequacy.

Elderly Care in China

After the establishment of the People's Republic of China in 1949, the responsibility for providing care and support to the country's elder people, orphans, and others in need was primarily rested with the family but the efforts done by family were supported by the social welfare system. The government took responsibility only of those who fall into the "three no's" categories, i.e. no family support, no ability to work, and no source of income. Such individuals were cared for in welfare institutions operated by local governments. Under the socialist system, there was restricted demand for social welfare services, and older people were expected to pursue care mainly from their family and work unit (Leung, 2010).

After the economic reforms of 1978, the Ministry of Civil Affairs (MCA) adopted market-oriented reforms. In 1980, there was shift in social welfare system and the Chinese government realized that it can no longer take sole responsibility for the provision of social care. The term Socialization of social welfare was introduced which apparently referred to the extension of welfare responsibilities beyond government to the wider society in the form of businesses, the family, and charities. It was the time when the concept of public-private partnership was introduced in the society to take care of elders. Specific changes were introduced to various welfare institutions including residential homes or community services for orphans, children, and adults with disabilities; and three no's elderly people. During those times, among the elderly population, only the "three nos" were given the opportunity by the state to stay in residential homes for free. Apart from them, all others had to pay specific fees to let the system run and to balance the scale of economy as well.

In the year 1998, the central government allowed private enterprises and non-government organizations to invest and operate social welfare services. In 2001, MCA published their Standards of Social Welfare Institutions for the Elderly to standardize service quality and management practices, including staffing, premises, the physical environment, and personal care services.

In 2002, the Ministry of Labor and Social Security issued Professional Standards of Care givers for Older Persons (Ministry of Labor and Social Security, 2002) which prescribed the detailed knowledge and skill requirements for the daily, medical, rehabilitation, and psychological care of older people. Since then, a series of laws, guidelines, and circulars had been promulgated to

regulate and improve the development of homes for the aged as a specific service category. City governments are encouraged to contract out or purchase services from NGOs. The overall approach is that central government will provide the policy direction and facilitation, and local government will experiment with different practice models.

Elderly Care Social Services in China

Accordingly, with the rules and regulations set by Ministry of Civil Affairs (MCA) for the delivery of elderly care services and the standards set by central government, the senior citizens are being offered two types of services i.e. Residential Care and Home Care Services.

Residential Care

Unlike in developed countries, residential care in China is loosely defined. It comprises a variety of settings, ranging from nursing homes to hostels, providing social care to older people who are either destitute or can pay the market fees. According to a national survey by the China National Committee on Aging, It is estimated that 16% of older people in cities and 15% in villages intend to live in a residential care facilities. However, the major reasons for older people to seek institutional care were as follows:

- ❖ Children unable to provide care
- ❖ Living in homes for the aged is better than at home
- ❖ Lot wishing to cause trouble to one's children

However, while choosing homes for the aged the major criteria include;

- ❖ Affordable fees
- ❖ Quality services
- ❖ Good living conditions
- ❖ Closeness to home

The above-mentioned reasons are interpreted as high percentage of older people prefer to stay in institutions probably reflects the expensive housing costs in many major cities in mainland China. The financial burden reduces the ability of the children to take care of their older parents. Some parents staying with their married child might consider moving to institutions so that their child can have more space at home and to avoid in-law conflict. (China National Committee on Aging, 2007a).

Generally, under the profound influence of traditional values, older people are reluctant to leave home and live in residential care homes. Under the market-driven policy, the relatively high fees such homes will charge mean that many cannot afford to do so anyway. There has been no objective assessment of older people's need for service support. All estimates to date have been based on surveys of expressed demand. More important, a recent national survey shows that over half of the current homes for the aged do not take in residents who cannot look after themselves (Q. Wu, 2011).

In 2006, 10 ministries and commissions jointly issued their Views on Speeding up the Development of Elderly Services. This suggests that the government should encourage multiple operational modes to facilitate the rapid provision and development of services for the elderly, such as contracting out services, providing subsidies, and giving support. Views includes the following points (Leung, 2010):

- ❖ Local government should ensure adequate care support for older people within the three nos.
- ❖ NGOs should be encouraged to provide residential, educational, and entertainment services for older people.
- ❖ The unemployed and people who have been laid off should be recruited as care workers.
- ❖ A variety of home care services, including daily and home care, counseling, rehabilitation, and emergency services should be developed.
- ❖ Medical care and hospice services should be explored.
- ❖ The quality of care workers should be enhanced through in-service training.
- ❖ Funding sources for elderly service should be diversified. Local government should provide a variety of preferential policies, such as land, premises, utility charges, and tax incentives to encourage NGOs and the private sector to operate residential services for older people.

Despite the fact that social welfare institutions have become increasingly specialized in providing residential care for older people, and such services have become more diverse so as to cater to the multiple needs of the frail elderly, a formal classification of residential care services according to their function remains underdeveloped in China.

Home Care Services

According to a study conducted in China, there is a dire need for home care services in urban China as many of the older people have certain daily needs that require formal assistance. Also a lot of senior citizens need someone to help them with domestic chores, personal care and social conversation. The study also has estimated that current urban home care services can only satisfy a chunk of the above stated needs and demands (Q. Yen, 2008). It is also observed that due to lack of availability of quality home care services, lots of senior citizens refuse to leave hospital after medical treatment. This is an emerging trend and is only because of the lack of community-based elderly care services at home.

Generally the strategy for the development of services for senior citizens in China has always been that “home care will be the foundation, community care will provide the necessary support, and residential care will be supplementary” and this was reiterated as the basic social policy directive in the 12th five year plan of the Central Government of China (2011–2015; Q. Wu, 2011). A range of community support services to older people, such as homemaking and meal delivery, transportation and escort services, rehabilitation care, and spiritual support (China National Committee on Aging, 2009). Daycare centers have been developed to serve weak senior citizens whose families cannot take care of them during the working hours on week days.

In 2001, the Ministry of Civil Affairs (MCA) initiated a project to assist local government in constructing and restructuring community-based activity centers to provide venues for elderly social activities, a platform for community care services, and support to home-based elderly care. In the first year of the implementation of the project centers were built in provincial capitals. In 2002, these facilitation centers were extended to major cities and additional centers were placed. These additional centers were formed in lower-level cities and townships. According to the MCA, more than 30 million senior citizens have benefited from these facilitation centers (MCA, 2010). The services provided by these facilitation centers included daily living support as well as medical and nursing care. In some neighborhoods, daycare, canteens, and respite services have also been developed. In 2008, the central government published its policy directive to strengthen home care services for senior citizens. The very next year, the China National Committee on Aging further announced policy directives to promote home care services to reiterate the priority for development. (China National Committee on Aging, 2009).

Senior Citizens in Pakistan

Pakistan is facing the population transition just like all other developing countries. The value systems which once dominated in Pakistani society are diminishing due to urbanization and shrinking family structures. Therefore, the senior citizens are posed as helpless and problematic for the caretakers. Both the government and private sectors have ignored this field to the extreme. In order to tailor the socio-economic desires of the elderly population of Pakistan, a comprehensive enumeration of the senior citizens, the trends and needs in the future should be taken care of accordingly. These efforts shall highlight further ways in this field from new dimensions.

Primarily, Pakistan is a Muslim state where family system is influenced by Islamic culture and Islamic values, where respect, care and sharing for each other are basic norm. However, due to the influx of western media and other external influences we see and find western family patterns being more attractive. It is broadly understood that the younger generations want to be more independent and the newly married couples like to live alone and do not want to live with their parents for matter of privacy to avoid family nuisance.

The falling birth rates and rising life expectancy rates have resulted in increase of the dependency ratios of the senior citizens. Urbanization has led to a breakdown of traditional norms as the metropolitan cultural forces lead to a greater valuation of privacy and has resulted in substantial shift towards nuclear rather than joint family systems. The same trends have been observed in China after 1978 and 1980s due to boost in economic activity in the result of urbanization and internal migration.

Our elderly parents, who have raised us from child to a man have invested years in our upbringing, are left in lurch in spite of their expectations that the children will support during old age. Majority of them are suffering daily problems of life, which due to old age they cannot attend to, keeping their hopes and eyes towards some sort of care they deserve. Seeing the loopholes in public policy and flaws of social security system, standardized and quality oriented elderly care social services is a farfetched dream.

Elderly Care in Pakistan

As Pakistan sees greater economic development, it is likely to witness more independent living and a decline in the bonding between generations. With a shift in cultural values as well as greater

economic pressures on the younger generations, elderly care will always suffer unless provisions are made for by the federal Government as we have seen in case of China where central government acts as regulatory body and the social services are more decentralized with provincial and local governments being encouraged to develop elderly care services. At present, the maximum care given to health issues of senior citizens is at the large public and private hospitals in this country's larger cities. Pakistani society mainly relies on co-residence with family and kin for elderly care. With most of the senior citizens that co-reside with their sons, delivery of elderly care extends from fulfilment of economic needs, healthcare as well as emotional needs.

There is requirement for the systematic documentation of the needs of the senior citizens. Here, social security, health insurance, quality of public services, old-age homes and geriatrics units in hospitals all matter. For instance, geriatric diseases such as memory dysfunction, Alzheimer's disease and orthopedic issues require training and recruitment of specialist doctors in the public sector, with incentives also being provided for the private sector. The distribution of such services across the whole country, in both rural and urban areas, is especially important. Similarly, community centers where trained workers provide care and counselling services also need to be established.

Since loneliness tends to be a major issue among the elderly, lessons could be learned from more developed Western European nations that pair day-care facilities and elderly centers together. The taboo against old-age homes that exist in our society needs to be tackled. Rather than the current practice of the elderly living alone when they can afford it, but still battling loneliness and, worse still, abandonment and subsequent residence at centers such as those established by Edhi, we should be looking to establish state-sponsored old-age homes. Here, the needs of both who wish to be in such homes, as well as those who are forced by their circumstances, must be catered for. This will become especially important as our population gradually ages, and economic pressures on younger individuals see a drying up of private funds for the elderly.

Elderly Care Social Services in Pakistan

The elderly care social welfare services in Pakistan are mainly termed as government based services and non-government organization (NGO) based services. The Government of Pakistan along with NGOs and Civil Society of Pakistan from time to time have made efforts to address the issues of senior citizens. However, these efforts did not receive any execution as no law has been

passed to put force into such decree. Individual level attentions have also been paid to the issue and some NGOs, private companies and clubs started giving some relaxation to the senior citizens but such initiatives are not enough to the growing population of senior citizens.

Public Sector Initiatives

In August 2004, the federal government approved a comprehensive relief package for senior citizens to provide basic needs of life on concessional basis and ensure their due respect and honor in the society. The package was prepared to save the senior citizens from the unpleasant situation in the hospitals and banks and to provide them special care. The senior citizens were supposed to be given priority at the railway stations, airports, hospitals and banks. The package also includes legal facilitation for the senior citizens and all the courts and concerned departments would be directed to give priority in handling the cases of the senior citizens. However, this package always remained on documents and never got implemented.

In 2014 when the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) and Sindh provincial Governments took interest in the welfare of senior citizens. Both governments defined the age for senior citizens as 60 years envisage their interests to be guarded by special councils headed by the provincial social welfare ministers. The Senior Citizens Cards were proposed which will enable them to enjoy the available facilities offered to them. The both provincial governments propose better care for senior citizens at hospitals, and ascertain homes for them. These cards were supposed to entitle the holders to attain free entry to public museums, libraries, and parks. Moreover, separate counters at hospitals and concessions in medical charges were also proposed in the policy. However, like the previous policies, these services and facilities only exist on papers and almost nothing was done in real.

The issue of care, protection and well-being of the senior citizens has been addressed under the Public Sector Development Program (PSDP). This initiative by the government make arrangements for establishment of Senior Citizens homes to accommodate deprived, poor and homeless persons without support. This initiative also plans for the creation of Senior Citizen's clubs or centers at local government levels to make use of their life long practices, knowledge and expertise. Apart from providing institutional care to the needy senior citizens, government laid major emphasis on strengthening our traditional joint family system. Learning from the Chinese experience of market-oriented services, government has been planning for providing shelter

facilities to the retired persons at their own expenses. Also, special beds in the major public sector Hospitals will be reserved for elderly patients.

NGO Based Social Services

Besides the public sector, the private sector is progressively providing necessary health care facilities for elderly people. Non-Government Organizations like Edhi Welfare Trust (EWT) and Agha Khan Foundation (AKF) had been providing social services to senior citizens for a long time on nob-profit and charity basis.

The Edhi Welfare Trust (EWT) houses elderly who either have been left by their children at the mercy of the EWT or family and relatives who left their elderly and sick to get rid of them due to socio economic reason. The Agha Khan Foundation has established a senior citizen home in Karachi, the largest city in Pakistan. However, this center only accommodates senior citizens from a particular minority and others are not allowed.

Apart from these two organizations, a large number of small scale foreign and locally funded organizations are also running shelter homes across the country. Keeping in view the above facts in the context of Pakistan it seems that very little work has been done with regard to provide social security to the Senior Citizens.

Conclusion

It seems that in Pakistan only political slogan, speeches and suggestion exists but no policy frame work is established or put forward for proper implementation. Though some social workers and NGOS have been working in this filed but their number was negligible and their working was limited, as such no significant contribution is seen towards community participation in this area.

In comparison to the majority of nations, policy work appears to have been done at Government level. American & European Countries are working towards protection, facilities and rights of their aging population. China is the most rapidly developing country and a proper social security exists due to the proper policy and guidelines of the central government. Although China also faces lots of challenges in terms of services provided to senior citizens majorly due to increase in ratio of the aging of its population, yet there is a lot in terms of policy making and policy implementation that government of Pakistan can learn from them.

The prospects of elderly care services in Pakistan depends on the commitment and ability of the government in meeting the challenges of insufficient funds for social services, inadequate and low-quality provision, and the lack of seriousness in making and implementing social policy for the betterment of senior citizens. As for now, it is clear that the capacity of NGOs and other charitable organizations are still underpeopled. In such scenario, the future of elderly care and the development of proper social welfare services in Pakistan is a farfetched dream. In order to have standardized elderly care services in Pakistan, the federal, provincial and city district governments need to join hands with NGOs and Civil Society to formulate and design and implement policy. Without government's intervention, such services at affordable rates cannot be offered to the senior citizens of Pakistan.

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